

Introducing the DE-RISK Project

Launched in October 2022, the DE-RISK Project aims to promote the adoption of local flexibility markets (LFMs) to ensure the secure and efficient distribution of renewable energy systems. The project is set to be completed in September 2025.

By encouraging the uptake of local flexibility markets, DE-RISK seeks to unlock up to 100 GW of flexibility by 2030 and facilitate the reliable integration of renewable energy systems into the grid. Through a user-centric approach that promotes behavioural change and reduces investment and implementation risks, DE-RISK will work to build trust among end users and foster active participation in flexibility markets. Digital twins of buildings, citizens, and the grid will help close the gap between simulation and real-world implementation, enabling the identification and mitigation of potential risks throughout planning and operational phases. These digital models will be integrated into a central Flexibility Platform.

WHAT IS A LOCAL FLEXIBILITY MARKET?

A local flexibility market enables customers to adjust when and how much electricity they consume or generate, often in return for financial compensation. These markets help optimise network capacity and improve the efficiency and resilience of local electricity systems.

WHAT IS RENEWABLE ENERGY?

Renewable energy refers to power derived from naturally replenished sources that are continuously or periodically accessible. The defining characteristic of renewable energy is its sustainability. Sources such as solar, wind, biomass, geothermal, and wave energy are naturally occurring and widely available.

As global population and consumption patterns evolve, energy demand continues to rise. Currently, fossil fuels remain the dominant source of energy; however, their non-renewable nature and significant environmental impact pose major challenges. Transitioning to renewables is essential to addressing both energy security and climate goals.

What Does the DE-RISK Project Aim to Achieve?

- ✔ **Behavioural Insights for Market Participation**
Using an innovative behavioural analysis methodology, the project will assess user needs and expectations, applying these insights to foster more active participation in local flexibility markets.
- ✔ **Digital Twins for Validation**
A cost-effective digital twin platform will be deployed in four distinct EU regions to assess, validate, and unlock local flexibility potential under diverse geographical, climatic, and regulatory conditions.
- ✔ **Collaborative Governance**
The project will convene key stakeholders from local, national, and EU levels in targeted workshops designed to evaluate and enhance the development of local flexibility frameworks.
- ✔ **Business Models and Financing Mechanisms**
DE-RISK will support the long-term viability of flexibility markets through the creation of innovative business models and financial tools—including crowdfunding, debt instruments, energy performance contracts, and P2P credit solutions.

Multi-Level Business Models:

New models providing long-term and sustainable benefits across the local flexibility value chain.

Customer Behaviour Journey:

Applications that enhance user interaction and encourage active participation in flexibility markets

Digital Twin Flexibility Platform:

High-accuracy simulations to reduce investment, implementation, and operational risks.

Local Flexibility Market Regulatory Package:

A framework that promotes fairness and competitiveness in the operation and adoption of local markets.

Financing Planning Package:

Tools and packages to democratise access to sustainable investment opportunities.

Validation through Pilot Projects:

Four pilot implementations across Türkiye, Spain, and Ireland to test and validate project components.

Weglobal

Weglobal applies advanced technologies to deliver development solutions across various sectors and regions. The organization focuses on inclusive approaches that integrate human-centered skills to support effective and fair change.

<https://weglobal.org>

Que Technologies

Que Technologies is a consulting, engineering, and product development firm focused on creating innovative solutions that enhance how people interact with their environment.

<https://www.que-tech.com>

Troya Environment Association

Troya Environment Association works on climate change and its local and national impacts. Since its founding, it has focused on climate and energy-related issues.

<https://troyacevre.org>

UEDAŞ

UEDAŞ provides reliable and efficient energy distribution services in the provinces of Bursa, Balıkesir, Çanakkale, and Yalova, with an emphasis on service quality and customer satisfaction.

<https://www.uedas.com.tr>

University of Galway

The University of Galway is internationally recognized for its commitment to sustainability. It is ranked among the top institutions worldwide and in Europe by Times Higher Education and serves as an SDG Champion in Ireland.

<https://www.universityofgalway.ie>

NOVA IMS – Nova University of Lisbon

NOVA IMS is the School of Information Management and Data Science at Nova University of Lisbon. Founded in 1989, the school trains professionals in information management and the strategic use of information technologies.

<https://www.novaims.unl.pt>

MIWenergia

MIWenergia is an electricity retailer in Spain offering services that support the energy transition. The company focuses on renewable energy and energy efficiency for households, businesses, and organizations.

<https://www.miwenergia.com>

R2M Solution

R2M Solution is a research and innovation company developing and implementing technologies that address societal challenges, with an emphasis on opportunity, responsibility, and real-world impact.

<https://www.r2msolution.com>

SEA SOFENA – Sofia Energy Agency

SEA SOFENA is a non-profit, non-governmental organization focused on sustainable energy, energy efficiency, renewable sources, and clean technologies.

<https://sofena.com/en>

Ecrowd

Ecrowd is a European Crowdfunding Service Provider (ECSP) licensed by ESMA. Based in Barcelona, it finances sustainable and positive-impact projects through its online platform.

<https://www.ecrowdinvest.com/ens>

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The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon EUROPE Programme under grant agreement No. 101075515